

A history of World Council for Curriculum and Instruction Philippines' Student Teachers Network and its contributions to teaching

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Abstract

The World Council for Curriculum and Instruction is recognized by the United Nations in consultative status with the Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) as a transnational educational organization committed in its mission to advancing the achievement of a just and peaceful world community and promoting person-to-person and professional relationships. The WCCI in the Philippines is composed of educators and professionals from all over the Philippines who join together in this person-to-person, non-governmental, and non-profit global organization, committed to active participation in efforts to achieve the purposes of the organization. The WCCI Philippines Student Teachers Network was established in 2011 primarily to develop excellent teachers who will be demonstrating their leadership skills in their professional life, which exposed them to the WCCI Special Interest Groups and motivated them to get actively involved in the current and future WCCI organization. The student officers were involved in the planning of the annual convention themes and objectives with varied committees. The participants were exposed to big and small group collaborative activities in varied special interest groups. It could therefore be concluded that varied roles and skills have been demonstrated by 21st Century learners and teachers. It is recommended that the organization should continue the active involvement of the education students in specific activities in varied capacities as members, officers, advisers, and researchers among others.

Keywords: World Council for Curriculum and Instruction; Student teachers; Contributions; Teaching.

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Introduction

The World Council for Curriculum and Instruction is a transnational educational organization committed to advancing the achievement of a just and peaceful world community through collaboration in curriculum and instruction projects, dialogues on educational and social issues of a global nature, the exchange of ideas, concerns, and solutions to problems, and person-to-person contacts and professional relationships.

The WCCI Philippine Student Teachers' Network (WCCI PSTN) was organized to prepare the student teachers for becoming excellent teachers in the profession via exposure to varied future teachers' roles as well as self-confidence to demonstrate their 21st century skills in today's curriculum landscape and a degree of high satisfaction in the students' roles and positive readiness to future teachers' skills and challenges. The WCCI PSTN National Conferences (starting from 2011) have provided varied opportunities to the Filipino student teachers the following:

- a. Planning the relevant annual student teachers' conferences;
- b. Preparing all the materials needed;
- c. Inviting the guest speakers and facilitators based on expertise;

- d. Preparing the application with the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) for endorsement of the national conferences and signing of letters to the University Presidents and College of Education Deans;
- e. Administering the registration of student teachers, faculty members, and administrators in every national conference;
- f. Preparing all the needed materials to use before, during and after program;
- g. Preparing the student group facilitators and administering the whole flow of the program;
- h. Ensuring the participants' involvement in the whole program;
- i. Inviting student teachers for membership;
- j. Preparing the annual national leadership seminars for institutional representatives during summer;
- k. Creating students' pledges of involvement as in preparing modules and learning materials; and
- l. Following up students' pledged involvement in their chosen personal advocacies in varied places: home, school, community, national, and international.

Moreover, the mother organization in the Philippines as well as at the international level has opened students' involvement in the formation of global educators beyond borders with Kaohsiung Normal University in Kaohsiung, Taiwan; Alliant International University in San Diego, California, USA; and Maepra Fatima School in Bangkok, Thailand, which provided the twenty-one Filipino student teachers with their positive self-concept and acceptance of new challenges and wider perspectives of a forming global educator. The international mother organization had likewise opened the involvement of two Filipino student teacher officers to the International Biennial Conference held in Budapest, Hungary, on July 10-15, 2016 and in Rome, Italy, on July 14-20, 2018, which provided a much higher vision of an international interaction with educators from different parts of the world with appreciation and pride as Filipino student teachers as well as acceptance of the challenges of the current and future professional world.

Since 2011, Filipino student teachers' involvement in the WCCI PSTN has provided essential opportunities for the demonstration of the needed skills of 21st century teachers, such as collaboration skills, communication skills (both oral and written), critical thinking skills, planning relevant topics and materials, problem solving skills, presenting creative group outputs and relevant research topics, and conducting workshops to display their varied roles. Furthermore, the planned national conferences have provided better interpersonal relationships and lasting friendships among the delegates and officers over time.

The formation of the youth lay advisers among the past officers of the WCCI PSTN, which started in 2017, is an outstanding feature among the student teachers for demonstrating their passion, including enhancing digital literacy skills and maximizing time, expertise, and energies to assist the current student officers successfully and gratefully. They were even willing to share their resources for funds or prizes in their varied activities. It has indeed provided more challenges to the Convenor and Adviser during the planning and execution of the annual leadership seminars and elections for the new officers, and they have continued to attend the regular officers' meetings in the planning and execution of the programs.

These WCCI PSTN National Conventions prepared the student teachers for leadership in their professional life, which exposed them to the WCCI Special Interest Groups. Such special interest groups are Human Rights Education, Values Education, Special Education, Environmental Sustainability, Gender Equality, Global Citizenship, Information and Communication Technology, Mental Health, and Communication and Culture. Conventions are conducted via small group collaborative activities that make every member feel important, accepted, cherished, and challenged to demonstrate oral and written communication skills, critical thinking, and problem solving (Pedrajas, 2019). It also includes individual and group acceptance of their decisions, planning of their creative and doable presentations, making use of their resolutions, and motivations to get actively involved in the current and future WCCI organizations.

WCCI Conferences

Currently, ten national conferences were conducted, which involved from 200 to 550 student teachers with around 30 to 40 institutions in attendance. The WCCI Student Chapter officers have been involved in the caravan meetings and preparation for national conferences too. The first seminars and of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) Convention conducted the student teachers' paper presentations, workshop seminars, and sharing of their classroom initiatives.

These student officers are also involved during national conferences of the WCCI National Chapter. Whole-day national student leadership seminars and workshop sessions among the nominated officers were annually conducted too in varied institutions like St. Paul University of Manila, the National Teachers College, Adamson University, Centro Escolar University, St. Dominic College of Asia, and St. Joseph College of Quezon City, among others.

Three hundred and fifty (350) student teachers, five deans, and twenty faculty members were in attendance from 23 public and private institutions in the Philippines. One of the colleges with the greatest number of delegates was St. Dominic College of Asia, which was headed by Vice President for Academic Affairs Dr. Nilda W. Balsicas, who brought her forty education students to the convention. Beatrice Candaza, a fourth-year Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English student at Global City Innovative College, was elected as the first national president. Other institutions were the following: St. Joseph College, University of the East, Far Eastern University, Centro Escolar University, Providential College of Caloocan, St. Mary's College, Letran College, Roosevelt Memorial College, Adamson University, Trace College, Albury College, Our Lady of Salvation Foundation College in Tacloban City, Mindanao State University of Iligan City, Global Reciprocal College, La Consolacion College, Adventist University, Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Pasig, Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Maynila, Emilio Aguinaldo College, Pasig Catholic College, Cainta Catholic College, Batangas State University, Our Lady of Perpetual University System in Laguna, Miriam College, and St. Paul University of Manila. From then on, every summer, deans were requested to send two representatives: one senior and one junior student, to attend the annual leadership training seminars, at the end of which was the election of national officers for the school year.

The researcher accepted the invitation from the President of St. Dominic College of Asia as Dean of the School of Arts, Sciences, and Education (SASE) in 2012; thus, SDCA became the main sponsor institution of the WCCIPSTN from 2012 to 2014. In each annual convention, the participants were likewise made to choose the special interest groups based on their interests and advocacies. These are the following: Peace Education, Human Rights Education, Global Education, Environmental Sustainability, Special Education, Early Childhood Education, Values Education, Community Development, Media Literacy, and Arts and Culture.

During the first to third national conferences, professional experts were invited to facilitate the sessions to inspire the students to focus on the special interest groups, and then they came up with doable actions and projects according to their personal, family, community, and national perspectives. On the fourth to tenth national conferences, the convenor prepared a group of graduating students to assume the facilitator's role in each special interest group.

One of the special projects of the organization was the WCCI International Practice Teaching Program for the Formation of Global Teachers Beyond Borders. This took place between the Global City Innovative College and the Kaohsiung Normal University in Kaohsiung, Taiwan, headed by the International President, Dr. Vincent Shieh. Eleven graduating students were exposed to a one-month practice teaching in Kaohsiung, Taiwan, in 2011. The next exposure was the International Practice Teaching Program between Global City Innovative College and the Alliant International University in San Diego, California, USA, in 2012, with three Filipino graduating students. The schools St. Dominic College of Asia and Our Lady of Perpetual University System of Laguna also sent three graduating education students to Maepra Fatima School in Bangkok, Thailand, for a month-long practice teaching with cultural exposures

in 2013. Then Miriam College sent three graduate students to Alliant International University in San Diego, California, USA, in 2014.

The second national conference was held on February 16, 2012, with the theme “*Educating Teachers of the 21st Century Skills*.” A very well-planned program was implemented. Dr. Gregorio Andaman Jr. gave the opening remarks, and several professors were tapped as facilitators in varied special interest groups, like Prof. Josefa Dimalanta, Prof. Apolonio Silva, Mr. Jonathan Sta. Ana, Prof. Imelda San Diego, Prof. Jayzel Alam, and Prof. Jaime Jimenez, among others. The SDCA Education students therefore assumed the major committees by their respective areas: Invitation, Accommodation, Registration, Food, Program, Certificates, and Documentation. The third national convention was held with the theme “*Educating for Peace and Harmony with Earth and Ourselves*” on February 28, 2013, with Dr. Graciano C. Yumul Jr. as the Keynote Speaker. Meanwhile, the Fourth WCCI National Student Chapter Conference was held on September 28, 2014, with the theme “*Preparing Quality Teachers, Leaders and Researchers for the K-12 Enhanced Program*.”

In 2012-2013, Angela Valdizno from SDCA became the Acting President, graduated as Cum Laude, and partly shared her WCCI PSTN international exposure in Bangkok, Thailand, for a month of practice teaching with two other Dominicans and one student teacher from the Our Lady of Perpetual Help University System of Laguna. In 2013-2014, Dino Monasterio Sabino was overwhelmingly voted president. He has demonstrated a real commitment, passion, and loyalty in mobilizing his fellow officers for varied activities like leadership training programs, planning sessions, and the 2014 National Convention. Selected student teachers were made to attend the national conventions held in Meralco Multipurpose Hall, Pasig City, from 2012 to 2014. The fourth-year students were in charge of registration and certificate distribution; the sophomores were in charge of ushering the delegates to their respective seats and evaluation; the freshmen were in charge of food distribution, counting, and a healthy environment; and the juniors were in charge of the sounds, flow of the program, and election process. The SDCA officers and members felt a very high and great sense of fulfillment for doing their level best in their respective committees.

In 2014-2015, the elected national student officers under the leadership of Education Student President, Jose Marie O. Velasco, were all united and focused to conduct the WCCI 5th National and First ASEAN Student Teachers Conference with the theme “*Strengthening Teacher Education: WCCI Response to ASEAN Integration*” on October 2-3, 2015. The respective officers had assumed their major roles and responsibilities as treasurer from Adamson University for the collection and registration of conference fees and dormitories; secretary from St. Paul University of Manila for registration and certificates; public relations officer from Miriam College as Master of Ceremonies; and auditor from Batangas State University for the flow of expenses. This is made possible with the able assistance of St. Paul College of Pasig High School Principal, Sr. Teresita Agana and the school director, Sr. Dedicacion Rosario, together with the whole staff.

Senior student teachers from varied universities presented their research papers on varied topics as a contrastive analysis of the basic education curriculum between two countries. Students were free to choose whether they would present the following ASEAN countries: Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. Twenty-three juniors facilitated a one-hour workshop on the varied roles of a teacher as talent manager and event organizer via project method; teacher as a friend and beginning counselor via metacognitive approach; teacher as a leader and prayer partner via experiential approach; teacher as multiple intelligence developer and instructional materials maker via constructivist approach; teacher as a researcher via constructivist approach; and teacher as a facilitator and evaluator via inquiry approach.

Dr. Usep Suhud from the State University of Indonesia, together with around fifteen ASEAN graduate students from the Asian Social Institute, came in their national costumes. They led the whole assembly in a multi-faith prayer session for peace under the auspices of Dr. Genevieve B. Kupang. Speakers were former Ambassador Rosalinda Tirona on the ASEAN Plan for Integration; Dr. Ester Ogena, who dealt

with the ASEAN Roadmap on the Teacher Education Curriculum; Dr. Allan De Guzman on ASEAN research skills and studies; and Sr. Flor Deza on One ASEAN Integrated Community. Special interest groups in the form of research problems, data collection, concrete actions in their respective schools and communities, and personalized advocacies were presented. Among the expert facilitators invited for the special interest groups were Prof. Josephine Calamlam, Dr. Aurora Fulgencio, Prof. Awee Hibanada, and Mr. Jonathan Sta. Ana, Prof. Jayzel Alam, and Prof. Stella Galang. Overall evaluation in all aspects of this ASEAN convention, including the night activities and dormitory services, was excellent.

Annually, during the summer, the Education Deans were invited to send two officers each: one senior and one junior student, for leadership training seminars conducted by the outgoing officers from 2011 to 2016. An annual leadership training workshop and seminar was conducted in the summer at varied universities in the Philippines. The leadership training programs included self-introduction, sharing of interests and skills, exposure to the WCCI PSTN, understanding of the various special interest groups, demonstration of their social, intellectual, emotional, psychological, and physical aspects, and leadership skills. The culmination is the election of national officers for the academic year.

The 2016 WCCI PSTN National Convention was held in Henry Sy Innovation Center, Miriam College, Quezon City with the theme “*The Role of Education for Global Citizenship in Promoting Social, Economic and Environmental Justice*,” in which three hundred education students from 25 institutions were involved. The officers have overwhelmingly involved the student delegates in planning their personal and communal advocacies: Peace Education, Human Rights, Special Education, Values Education, Gender Equality, Global Citizenship, Cultural Communication, Environmental Sustainability, and Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Literacy Skills.

Moreover, it is noteworthy to mention that the roster of officers in the academic year 2016–2017 has worked dynamically and with high spirits to conduct four caravans on peace education with student teachers in attendance. They held peace caravans at National Teachers’ College on September 9, 2016, with 200 attendees and the full support of former Dean Dr. Edna R. Galiza; and at Philippine Women’s University on September 30, 2016, with 185 attendees and the positive response of former Dean Dr. Erlinda D. Serrano and St. Paul University of Tuguegarao on October 29, 2016, with 300 attendees and the generous accommodation and sponsorship of President Sr. Merceditas Ang, and in Miriam College on April 13, 2017, with 285 attendees and the enthusiastic support of former Dean Rose Aligada and Dr. Trixie Sison, Chair of the Early Childhood Education.

From 2017 to 2021, the past top outgoing officers Sean Lopez, Ivannah Uy, Christian Cahilig, Erica Mae Caparros, Prences Joy Layco, Lester Gatchalian, Jose Marie Velasco, Rebecca Pineda, and Dino Sabino formed a group of lay youth advisers with whom they primarily conducted the National Officers’ Leadership Seminars and assisted in the mechanics of the organization. The activities for the leadership activities, with all the necessary materials, were excellently prepared and implemented.

The 2017 WCCI PSTN National Convention with the theme “*The Role of Peace Education in the 21st Century Teacher Curriculum*” was held at Adamson University with around two hundred fifty student participants. Dr. Genevieve Kupang was invited as the guest workshop facilitator. With this exposure, varied peace education caravans were conducted in different colleges and universities: National Teachers’ College on September 9, 2017, with 200 student teachers in attendance; Philippine Women’s University in Manila on September 30, 2017, with 185 student teachers; and at St. Paul University Philippines, Tuguegarao City, Cagayan on October 29, 2017, with 350 student teachers.

The convention was also held in Centro Escolar University, Manila on September 22, 2017, with a theme “*SEAMEO INNOTECH: Flexible Learning for the 21st Century ASEAN Learners*” with Mr. Juan Robertino Macalde, SEAMEO Innotech Specialist as the main facilitator with 250 students in attendance. Different creative presentations of their chosen advocacies were likewise witnessed with their newly formed acquaintances. This opportunity had indeed prepared these student teachers to accept new friendships with genuine sincerity and an openness to share themselves.

The organizers were able to get 72 student teachers from the Philippines during the WCCI-ASEAN Conference on August 17-19, 2017, in the Novotel Araneta Center, Cubao, Quezon City, Philippines. Officers and other school student leaders have been assigned to assist and communicate with the delegates from different countries. Students said that they were accepted and felt important for the varied professional tasks they did as participants. At the same time, they were challenged to perform unique tasks as they shared their talents and abilities in front of the delegates.

The 2018 WCCI PSTN National Convention with the theme “*Strengthening Youth Leadership: Forging Values Formation, Peace Making, Community Development, and Environmental Care*” was held in SM Aura Premier in Taguig City with around 450 delegates from forty universities in the Philippines including four Brunei student delegates and a college dean, and around thirty college administrators and faculty members from varied institutions in the Philippines. The committee had four student leaders from Lourdes College of Cagayan De Oro, Miriam College, St. Paul University Philippines, Tuguegarao City, and Providential College. Former Senator-in-Charge of Education Chiz Escudero was the guest speaker who conducted a dialogue with the student teachers and educators on the impact of K–12 education in the Philippines as it affects the curriculum, faculty, facilities, and learning materials they use in the classroom.

The committee members were indeed focused on the implementation of their roles and responsibilities to ensure the success of the whole program. A field trip was conducted before the convention in Taguig City, where it witnessed community projects in the utilization of water lilies into varied products such as bags, folders, writing pads, house and office decorations, costumes, and art panels, as well as paying a visit to important national sites such as *Libingan ng mga Bayani*, American Cemetery, and Science in the Park.

During the pandemic, fifteen student teachers from different universities shared their short videos on how they were managing themselves in their academic work during the organization’s national webinar held on August 28, 2021. Generally, the students have shared their acceptance of the situations and how they managed the unprecedented situations intellectually, socially, emotionally, psychologically, physically, economically, academically, and spiritually in all aspects of the educational environment.

Eighteen educational institutions in the Philippines also participated in the virtual celebrations. It welcomed some universities, which are listed as: Bukidnon State University, Western Visayas State University, Technological Institute of the Philippines (Manila and Quezon City Campuses), Polytechnic University of the Philippines Manila, Benguet State University, University of the East Manila, St. Mary’s University, and University of the Philippines—Diliman. Student leaders came up with the whole month of national election registration campaigns among the youth for active involvement. Celebrations of National Teachers’ Month and World Teachers’ Day were conducted via national contests such as the National Photoshoot, National Essay Writing, and National Poster Making.

For Academic Year 2021-2022, Youth Lay Advisers and Officers conducted another National Webinar with the theme “*Teachers of Tomorrow: Realizing Resiliency, Compassion, and Dedication Amidst the Pandemic*” on November 20, 2021, with two hundred fifty student teachers, ten school deans, and sixteen faculty members in attendance from forty institutions all over the Philippines. The guest speaker was Sr. Merceditas Ang, SPC, the current National President of the WCCI Philippines and President of St. Paul University Philippines, Tuguegarao City, was cited as the Leadership Global Educator in India during an International Gathering of Educators. The speaker gave a very challenging message to the participants on the roles of educators during the pandemic.

Seven special interest groups were able to facilitate successfully through the establishment of interpersonal relationships among the members, focusing on each advocacy with a concrete, doable program of activities for the year and for life. Various group commendations were given as the following: Most Comprehensive Program, Most Relevant Program, Most Talented Program, Most Creative Group, Most Participative Group, Most Challenging Group, and Most Active Group. As regards to the National

Webinar held on November 20, 2021, students, faculty, and administrators had made the following evaluations:

- Relevance of the program – 4.8 (Excellent)
- Relevance to the participants – 4.9 (Excellent)
- Degree of participants' involvement – 5.0 (Excellent)
- Importance of the whole activity to the participants – 5.0 (Excellent)

Special interest group members have established a higher degree of cooperation by interacting among themselves prior to the national webinar date. They had made extra effort to introduce themselves among the members of the group, shared their views about the chosen or assigned special interest group, and came up with a possible impact by coming up with a concrete view with identified vision, objectives, and doable activities for the semester for themselves as they affect other persons in the home, school, community, national, and international perspectives.

Discussion

The organization has acknowledged officers' exemplary leadership performances at the national level, which were communicated to their respective institutions as National Leadership Awards during graduation ceremonies. The basis of leadership awards consists of passion for vision, a person-oriented goal, determination, dedication, enthusiasm, energy, compassion, and gratitude. Some of these are identical to what James MacGregor Burns described as transformational leaders in 1978. These kinds of leaders are concerned and involved in the process; they are also focused on helping every member of the group succeed as well. Moreover, Burns says that transformational leadership can be seen when leaders and followers make each other advance to a higher level of morale and motivation. Moreover, Bass and Riggio (2006) said that transformational leadership can be defined based on the impact that it has on followers. Transformational leaders, as suggested by Masood et al. (2006), garnered trust, respect, and admiration from their followers.

These student teachers who have been involved in the WCCI PSTN Annual National Conventions, Caravans, Group Dynamics Activities, Formation of Global Educators Beyond Borders, and International and National Conferences of the mother organization have demonstrated their genuine aspiration to focus, collaborate, cooperate, think critically, solve problems, discuss matters critically, relevantly, and creatively with their fellow student teachers, and identify the ideas from guest speakers, administrators, faculty members, and fellow participants. Student teachers have likewise demonstrated to some extent a variety of learning techniques, methods, outputs, assessment tools, and online digital literacy skills in their becoming 21st century learners and teachers (Ang, 2017; Jaiswal, 2019).

Gagne's (1916–2002) nine events of instruction, including Ausebel's theory (1967), focused on meaningful learning as a clearly articulated and precisely differentiated conscious experience that emerges when potentially meaningful signs, symbols, concepts, or propositions are related to and incorporated within a given individual's cognitive structure (Agra et al., 2019). Bruner (1961) further proposes that learners construct their own knowledge and do this by organizing information using a coding system. He believed that the most effective way to develop learning is through discovery, as illustrated by the student teachers, which will assist them in their roles as facilitators, community developers, and leaders of the classroom, school, and community (Ozdem-Yilmaz & Bilican, 2020).

Conclusions and Recommendations

The World Council for Curriculum and Instruction Student Teachers' Network in the Philippines has offered enough challenges and opportunities to future teachers in three major roles as facilitators,

community leaders, and researchers. The mother organization of the Philippines has openly expressed their high commendations for the officers' passion, creativity, involvement, and excellent leadership and performances during this period.

The fact that ten former student teacher officers of the WCCI PSTN have volunteered to form themselves as youth lay advisers to the current officers since 2011 has indeed strengthened progressive and dynamic leadership and guidance among the officers and members. Student teachers' exposures to the international conferences in Budapest, Hungary, and Rome, Italy, have likewise broadened their perspectives as global educators and professional leaders.

Based on the conclusions above, the researcher recommended the following:

1. Continue the active involvement of the education students in specific WCCI activities in varied capacities as members, officers, advisers, and researchers among others.
2. Continue inviting more institutions for the future educators' involvement in varied advocacies aligned in the United Nations Development Standards 2030 Sustainable Goals.
3. Renew / activate the formation of global educators beyond borders among the graduating student teachers after the pandemic.
4. Conduct a possible study on the quantitative and qualitative impact of WCCI PSTN Officers and members' involvement to their current professional development program.

References

- Agra, G., Formiga, N. S., Oliveira, P. S. D., Costa, M. M. L., Fernandes, M. D. G. M., & Nóbrega, M. M. L. D. (2019). Analysis of the concept of meaningful learning in light of the Ausubel's Theory. *Revista Brasileira De Enfermagem*, 72(1), 248-255. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0034-7167-2017-0691>
- Ang, S. M. (2017). Responding to the educational challenges and opportunities of ASEAN integration: A case analysis of St. Paul University Philippines. *Asian Education Studies*, 2(4), 19-26. <https://doi.org/10.20849/aes.v2i4.257>
- Bass, B. M., & Riggio, R. E. (2006). *Transformational leadership* (2nd ed.). Psychology Press.
- Bruner, J. S. (1961). The act of discovery. *Harvard Educational Review*, 31, 21-32.
- Jaiswal, P. (2019). Using learner-centered instructional approach to foster students' performances. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 9(9), 1074-1080. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17507/tpls.0909.02>
- Masood, S. A., Dani, S. S., Burns, N. D., & Backhouse, C. J. (2006). Transformational leadership and organizational culture: The situational strength perspective. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part B: Journal of Engineering Manufacture*, 220(6), 941-949. <https://doi.org/10.1243/09544054JEM499>
- Ozdem-Yilmaz, Y., & Bilican, K. (2020). Discovery Learning—Jerome Bruner. In B. Akpan & T. J. Kennedy (Eds.), *Science education in theory and practice: An introductory guide to learning theory* (pp. 177-190). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-43620-9_13
- Pedrajas, T. P. (2019). Experiences of collaborative research among students: Insights, challenges, and applications of SDCA life formula. *SDCA Journal of Education*, 4, 27-33. <https://sites.google.com/sdca.edu.ph/sdca-rdo/publications/sdca-journal-of-education/sdca-jed-volume-4-2019/experiences-of-collaborative-research-among-students>